

DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILL OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS OF B1 LEVEL THROUGH MOBILE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: Both learning and teaching processes are becoming easy and effective with the help of mobile application and various platforms. The majority of the applications offer new methods and functions of developing speaking skill of the learners therefore the efficiency of the apps is increasing day by day. Moreover, learners who face challenges connected with pronunciation and grammar, can find a way to cope with them through mobile application aid.

Key words: learners, speaking skill, mobile applications, proper techniques.

INTRODUCTION:

In this ever-developing world the role of both language and accessibility is becoming crucial due to the modernization of the new generation. In comparison with the past ancestor's opportunities, now the learning style and importance has undergone a great deal of changes and the demand for multilingualism is increasing respectively. Moreover, learning a language is not as difficult as it seemed before, grateful to our intelligent scientists we are given a chance to utilize various gadgets and mobile applications in order to gain knowledge even being on the other side of the world, through online classes and in appropriate time with highly motivative methods.

Mobile apps which are regarded as software applications can be installed just with a few clicks of the button either in smartphones, tablets and even in computers and laptop, it is not necessary to be compiled to one place. As it stated by Ramya G and Madhumathi P "The very term 'mobile' stands for the 'mobility' or the ability to move freely and easily from one place to another"[2]. Though speaking in a foreign language sounded as a horror for some people a decade ago, at present there are the apps which can aid to improve speaking ability with effective feedback. A number of learners whom are learning a language in most of cases neglect speaking since they feel strong fear of making a mistake or using improper grammar structure, all these factors are due to lack of practices, even those who attend educational centers are practiced individually by sitting in front of the teacher, because of the majority of people and it is impossible to work only with one learner.

However, many mobile application propose an opportunity to enable them to practice 4 skills of English (speaking, writing, listening and reading). Mobile applications propose a number of effective features that are useful for learners to make the process of learning easier and provides them to get both feedback and errors which need to be improved. According to Dana Lindaman and Dan Nolan "The relative ease of use associated with mobile devices allows users to interact with the content without thinking about the device as a computer" [1]. This viewpoint highlights that while learning materials relating to the language on mobile phones one can unconsciously learn the language and also use his/her smartphones in a beneficial way not just play games or watch videos.

The list of games which are helpful to improve speaking skill:

- Duolingo

This mobile application offers a number of various functions to improve both speaking and pronunciation and in return provides with feedback. The majority number of people face challenges in correcting pronunciation and grammar whereas Duolingo can be the most appropriate version for them because there is the function giving feedback for the speech which is send to into speech. Moreover, this application is not only for those who tend to learn English but also the learners of more than 40 languages such as English, French, Chinese, Italian, Portuguese and others.

- Pimsleur

This platform is regarded as one of the most famous ones to improve the speaking skill of the learners and it is not only appropriate for speaking skill enhancement but also develops listening comprehension as well with the audio-based language courses. One of the unique features of Pimsleur program is the use of interval repetition, a method that involves repeating and reiterating language material at specific intervals to help learners remember information.

- Speechling

Without having feedback for the work that have been done it is difficult to learn anything properly therefore the program Speechling provides personalized feedback on pronunciation and offers conversation practice with tutors. Nowadays attending tutorial courses cost a high amount of money and for employees who work in lower posts it is difficult to pay half of their monthly salary for one course. However, the platform Speechling provides with opportunity to work with tutor's guidance and these courses are created to aid learners to improve their language skills trough one-to-one feedback from professional trainers.

There is no barrier for those who has strong desire to acquire knowledge in any sphere and N.N Kasatkina claimed that mobile apps "a looking forward method of learning, allowing you to learn the material at a convenient place and at a convenient time" [3]. Obviously, learning environment is any place where you can carry your mobile phon.

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